

Pythagorean Neutrosophic ideals of Near ring

A.Rajalakshmi ^{#1}, K. Lenin Muthu Kumaran ^{*2}

^{#1}*Department of Mathematics, Shanmuga Industries Arts & Science College, Affiliated to Thiruvalluvar University, Tiruvannamalai, Tamilnadu, India – 606603*

Abstract— In this article, we define pythagorean neutrosophic ideals of near-rings, image of pythagorean neutrosophic ideals and homomorphism of pythagorean neutrosophic ideals with suitable example. Aim of this research article is to prove intersection of two pythagorean neutrosophic ideals is also a pythagorean neutrosophic ideals and complement of pythagorean neutrosophic ideals is a pythagorean neutrosophic ideals. Finally we characterized these pythagorean neutrosophic ideals using level subsets and pre-image of homomorphism of pythagorean neutrosophic fuzzy ideals of near-ring is pythagorean neutrosophic fuzzy ideals of near-ring and it's converse is also true.

Keywords— Neutrosophic set, Pythagorean fuzzy set, Pythagorean neutrosophic set, Pythagorean neutrosophic ideals in near-ring.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fuzzy sets [21] have a great progress in every scientific research area. After the introduction of ordinary fuzzy sets, new extensions have appeared one by one in the literature. Among these extensions, picture fuzzy sets [5], neutrosophic sets [17], spherical fuzzy sets [8], pythagorean fuzzy sets [3], pythagorean neutrosophic sets [4] are the members of the same class since any element in these sets is represented by a membership degree, a non-membership degree and an indeterminacy degree assigned by independently. The pythagorean fuzzy set is proposed by Yager [19]. The notion of rough pythagorean sets was introduced by Hussain. A et al.[9] in the year 2019. The notion of fuzzy subnear-ring and ideal were first introduced by Abou-Zaid in [2] 1989. The notion of fuzzy ideals of near-rings with interval valued membership functions introduced by Davvaz [6] in 2001.

There are situations where sum of membership and non-membership value greater than one, unlike the cases capture in intuitionistic (IFSs). This limitation in IFS naturally led to a construct called pythagorean fuzzy sets (PFSs). Pythagorean fuzzy set (PFS) proposed in[3] is a new tool to deal with vagueness considering the membership grade P and non-membership grade R satisfying the notion or $P^2 + R^2 + \pi^2 \leq 1$, where π is the pythagorean fuzzy set index. The construct of PFSs can be used to characterize uncertain information more sufficiently and accurately than IFS to model the vagueness in the practical problem. Gundogdu and Kahraman [8] introduced the new concept of spherical fuzzy set and discuss the new operations. Smarandache [17] introduced the new concept of neutrosophic set. Khan et al. [13] introduced the neutrosophic N-structures and their application in semi groups. The neutrosophic theories have received greater attention in recent years. By developing it V.Chinnadurai and Arul selvam introduced the pythagorean neutrosophic ideals in semi group [4]. From all above we constructed a paper as follows: In section 2, the preliminaries and definitions are given additionally presented some algebraic structures of pythagorean fuzzy sets. In section 3, we studied the definition of pythagorean neutrosophic ideals (in short PNI) of a near-ring here we let pythagorean neutrosophic set is PNS and discussed some important properties of pythagorean neutrosophic ideals of a near-ring.

II. PRELIMINARIES

In this section, we recall some of basic definition and result of near-ring. They are

Definition 2.1.[14] A neutrosophic fuzzy subset $\mathfrak{S}$ of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$ is called a neutrosophic fuzzy subnear-ring of $\mathfrak{B}$ if

$$(1) P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha - \varphi) \geq \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\}$$

$$Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha - \varphi) \leq \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\}$$

$$R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha - \varphi) \leq \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\}$$

$$(2) P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \geq \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\}$$

$$Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \leq \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\}$$

$$R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \leq \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\}$$

A neutrosophic fuzzy subset $\mathfrak{S}$ of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$ is called a neutrosophic fuzzy ideal of near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$ if $\mathfrak{S}$ is a neutrosophic fuzzy subnear-ring of $\mathfrak{B}$ and

$$(3) P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) \geq P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha)$$

$$Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) \leq Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha)$$

$$R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) \leq R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha)$$

$$(4) P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \geq P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)$$

$$Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \leq Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)$$

$$R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \leq R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)$$

$$(5) P_{\mathfrak{S}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) \geq P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varepsilon)$$

$$Q_{\mathfrak{S}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) \leq Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varepsilon)$$

$$R_{\mathfrak{S}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) \leq R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varepsilon)$$

A neutrosophic fuzzy subset with above conditions (1),(2),(3) and (4) is called a neutrosophic fuzzy left ideal of near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$, where as (1),(2),(3) and (5) is called a neutrosophic fuzzy right ideal of near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$.

Definition 2.2.[4] Let W be a universe of discourse, a pythagorean fuzzy set (PFS) $\mathfrak{S} = \{\alpha, P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha) \mid \alpha \in W\}$ where $P_{\mathfrak{S}}: W \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $Q_{\mathfrak{S}}: W \rightarrow [0,1]$ represent the degree of membership and non-membership of the object $\alpha \in W$ to the set $\mathfrak{S}$ subset to the condition $0 \leq (P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha))^2 + (Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha))^2 \leq 1$ for all $\alpha \in W$. For the sake of simplicity a PFS is denoted as $\mathfrak{S} = (P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha))$.

Definition 2.3.[4] Let W be a universe of discourse, a pythagorean neutrosophic set (PNS) $\mathfrak{S} = \{\alpha, P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha) \mid \alpha \in W\}$ where $P_{\mathfrak{S}}: W \rightarrow [0,1]$, $Q_{\mathfrak{S}}: W \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $R_{\mathfrak{S}}: W \rightarrow [0,1]$ represent the degree of membership, non-membership and indeterminacy of the object $\alpha \in W$ to the set $\mathfrak{S}$ subset to the condition $0 \leq (P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha))^2 + (Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha))^2 + (R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha))^2 \leq 2$ for all $\alpha \in W$. For the sake of simplicity a PNS is denoted as $\mathfrak{S} = (P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha))$. Throughout this paper $\mathfrak{B}$ denotes left near-ring. In practice, may be for some reason, the condition $0 \leq P(\alpha), R(\alpha) \leq 1$, is not true. For instance, $0.5 + 0.6 = 1.1 > 1$ but $0.5^2 + 0.6^2 < 1$, or $0.4 + 0.6 > 1$ but $0.4^2 + 0.6^2 < 1$. To overcome this situation in 2013 Yager [19] introduced the concept of the pythagorean fuzzy set.

III. PYTHAGOREAN NEUTROSOPHIC IDEALS OF NEAR-RING

In this section, we introduce the notion of pythagorean neutrosophic ideals of near-ring. We characterize neutrosophic ideals using pythagorean logic in near-ring.

Definition 3.1. A pythagorean neutrosophic subset $\mathfrak{S}$ of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$ is called a pythagorean neutrosophic subnear-ring of $\mathfrak{B}$ if

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) & P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha - \varphi) \geq \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\
 & Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha - \varphi) \leq \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\
 & R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha - \varphi) \leq \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\
 (2) & P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \geq \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\
 & Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \leq \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\
 & R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \leq \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\}
 \end{aligned}$$

A pythagorean neutrosophic subset $\mathfrak{S}$ of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$ is called a pythagorean neutrosophic ideal of $\mathfrak{B}$ if $\mathfrak{S}$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic subnear-ring of $\mathfrak{B}$ and

$$\begin{aligned}
 (3) & P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) \geq P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha) \\
 & Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) \leq Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha) \\
 & R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) \leq R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha) \\
 (4) & P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \geq P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi) \\
 & Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \leq Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi) \\
 & R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \leq R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi) \\
 (5) & P_{\mathfrak{S}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) \geq P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varepsilon) \\
 & Q_{\mathfrak{S}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) \leq Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varepsilon) \\
 & R_{\mathfrak{S}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) \leq R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varepsilon)
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that $\mathfrak{S}$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic left ideal of $\mathfrak{B}$ if it satisfies (1),(2),(3) and (4) and $\mathfrak{S}$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic right ideal of $\mathfrak{B}$ if it satisfies (1),(2),(3) and (5).

Definition 3.2.

Let Y be a mapping from a non-empty set $\mathfrak{U}$ to a non-empty set $\mathfrak{B}$. Let $\mathfrak{S}$ be a pythagorean neutrosophic subset of $\mathfrak{U}$ and $\mathfrak{S}$ be a pythagorean neutrosophic subset of $\mathfrak{B}$. The image $Y(\mathfrak{S})$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic subset of $\mathfrak{B}$ defined by $Y(\mathfrak{S}) = \{ \langle \alpha, Y(P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha)), Y(Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha)), Y(R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha)) \rangle \mid \alpha \in \mathfrak{U} \}$,

where, $Y(P(\alpha)) = \begin{cases} \sup_{\varphi \in Y^{-1}(\alpha)} P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi) & \text{if } Y^{-1}(\alpha) \neq \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$
 $Y(Q(\alpha)) = \begin{cases} \inf_{\varphi \in Y^{-1}(\alpha)} Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi) & \text{if } Y^{-1}(\alpha) \neq \emptyset \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$
 $Y(R(\alpha)) = \begin{cases} \inf_{\varphi \in Y^{-1}(\alpha)} R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi) & \text{if } Y^{-1}(\alpha) \neq \emptyset \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Definition 3.3.

A map Y from a near-ring $\mathfrak{U}$ into a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$ is called homomorphism if

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y(\alpha + \varphi) &= Y(\alpha) + Y(\varphi) \text{ and} \\
 Y(\alpha \varphi) &= Y(\alpha)Y(\varphi) \text{ for all } \alpha, \varphi \in \mathfrak{U}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Let $\mathfrak{U}$ and $\mathfrak{B}$ be two non-empty set and $Y: \mathfrak{U} \rightarrow \mathfrak{B}$ be a function. If $\mathfrak{S}$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic set in $\mathfrak{B}$, then the pre-image of $\mathfrak{S}$ under Y , denoted by $Y^{-1}(\mathfrak{S})$, is a pythagorean neutrosophic set in $\mathfrak{U}$ defined by $Y^{-1}(\mathfrak{S}) = \{ \langle \alpha, Y^{-1}(P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha)), Y^{-1}(Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha)), Y^{-1}(R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha)) \rangle \mid \alpha \in \mathfrak{U} \}$, where

$$Y^{-1}(P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha)) = P_{\mathfrak{S}}(Y(\alpha)), Y^{-1}(Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha)) = Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(Y(\alpha)) \text{ and } Y^{-1}(R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha)) = R_{\mathfrak{S}}(Y(\alpha)).$$

Example 3.4. Let $\mathfrak{B} = \{v, \zeta, \tau, \kappa\}$ be a set with two binary operations defined as follows:

+	v	ζ	τ	κ
v	v	ζ	τ	κ
ζ	ζ	v	κ	τ
τ	τ	κ	ζ	v
κ	κ	τ	v	ζ

•	v	ζ	τ	κ
v	v	v	v	v
ζ	v	v	v	v
τ	v	v	v	v
κ	v	v	ζ	ζ

Then clearly $(\mathfrak{B}, +, \cdot)$ is a left near-ring. Define $P_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}}, R_{\mathfrak{S}}: \mathfrak{B} \rightarrow [0,1]$ by

$\frac{\nu}{(0.5,0.2,0.3)}, \frac{\zeta}{(0.3,0.4,0.4)}, \frac{\tau}{(0.1,0.6,0.6)}, \frac{\kappa}{(0.1,0.6,0.6)}$. It can be verify that $\{ \langle P_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}}, R_{\mathfrak{S}} \rangle \mid \alpha \in \mathfrak{B} \}$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic ideal of near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$.

Theorem 3.5

Let $\mathfrak{S} = (P_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}}, R_{\mathfrak{S}})$ be a pythagorean neutrosophic set in a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$. Then $\mathfrak{S}$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic ideal of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$ if and only if $P_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c$ and $R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c$ are neutrosophic ideals of $\mathfrak{B}$.

Proof.

Let $\mathfrak{S} = (P_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}}, R_{\mathfrak{S}})$ be a pythagorean neutrosophic ideal of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$. Then $P_{\mathfrak{S}}$ is a neutrosophic ideal of near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$. Now, for every $\alpha, \varphi, \varepsilon \in \mathfrak{B}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha - \varphi) &= 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha - \varphi) \\ &\geq 1 - \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\ &= \min\{1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\ &= \min\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\varphi)\} \\ R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha - \varphi) &= 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha - \varphi) \\ &\geq 1 - \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\ &= \min\{1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\ &= \min\{R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\varphi)\} \\ Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha \varphi) &= 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \\ &\geq 1 - \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\ &= \min\{1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\ &= \min\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\varphi)\} \\ R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha \varphi) &= 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \\ &\geq 1 - \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\ &= \min\{1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\ &= \min\{R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\varphi)\} \\ Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) &= 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) \\ &\geq 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha) \\ &= Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha) \\ R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) &= 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) \\ &\geq 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha) \\ &= R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha) \\ Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha \varphi) &= 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \\ &\geq 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi) \\ &= Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\varphi) \\ R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha \varphi) &= 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \\ &\geq 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi) \\ &= R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\varphi) \\ Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) &= 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) \\ &\geq 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varepsilon) \\ &= Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\varepsilon) \\ R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) &= 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) \\ &\geq 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varepsilon) \\ &= R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\varepsilon) \end{aligned}$$

Hence $Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c$ and $R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c$ are neutrosophic ideal of $\mathfrak{B}$.

Conversely, assume that $P_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c$ and $R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c$ are neutrosophic ideals of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$.

For every $\alpha, \varphi, \varepsilon \in \mathfrak{B}$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha - \varphi) &\geq \min\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\varphi)\} \\ 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha - \varphi) &\geq \min\{1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\ &= 1 - \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\ \text{Therefore } Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha - \varphi) &\leq \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\ R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha - \varphi) &\geq \min\{R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\varphi)\} \\ 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha - \varphi) &\geq \min\{1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\ &= 1 - \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\ \text{Therefore } R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha - \varphi) &\leq \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\ Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha \varphi) &\geq \min\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\varphi)\} \\ 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) &\geq \min\{1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\ &= 1 - \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\ \text{Therefore } Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) &\leq \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\ R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha \varphi) &\geq \min\{R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}}^c(\varphi)\} \\ 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) &\geq \min\{1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= 1 - \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\
\text{Therefore } R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) &\leq \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\
Q_{\mathfrak{S}^c}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) &\geq Q_{\mathfrak{S}^c}(\alpha) \\
1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) &\geq 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha) \\
\text{Therefore } Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) &\leq Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha) \\
R_{\mathfrak{S}^c}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) &\geq R_{\mathfrak{S}^c}(\alpha) \\
1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) &\geq 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha) \\
\text{Therefore } R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) &\leq R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha) \\
Q_{\mathfrak{S}^c}(\alpha \varphi) &\geq Q_{\mathfrak{S}^c}(\varphi) \\
1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) &\geq 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi) \\
\text{Therefore } Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) &\leq Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi) \\
R_{\mathfrak{S}^c}(\alpha \varphi) &\geq R_{\mathfrak{S}^c}(\varphi) \\
1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) &\geq 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi) \\
\text{Therefore } R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) &\leq R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi) \\
Q_{\mathfrak{S}^c}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) &\geq Q_{\mathfrak{S}^c}(\varepsilon) \\
1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) &\geq 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varepsilon) \\
\text{Therefore } Q_{\mathfrak{S}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) &\leq Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varepsilon) \\
R_{\mathfrak{S}^c}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) &\geq R_{\mathfrak{S}^c}(\varepsilon) \\
1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) &\geq 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varepsilon) \\
\text{Therefore } R_{\mathfrak{S}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) &\leq R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varepsilon)
\end{aligned}$$

Hence the pythagorean neutrosophic set $\mathfrak{S} = (P_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}}, R_{\mathfrak{S}})$ be a pythagorean neutrosophic ideal of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$.

□

Definition 3.6.

Let PNS $\mathfrak{S} = (P_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}}, R_{\mathfrak{S}})$. Then we define three operation on $\mathfrak{S}$ as follows:

- (1) $\diamond \mathfrak{S} = \langle P_{\mathfrak{S}}, P_{\mathfrak{S}^c} \rangle$, where $P_{\mathfrak{S}^c}(\alpha) = 1 - P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha)$
- (2) $\square \mathfrak{S} = \langle Q_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}^c} \rangle$, where $Q_{\mathfrak{S}^c}(\alpha) = 1 - Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha)$
- (3) $\Delta \mathfrak{S} = \langle R_{\mathfrak{S}}, R_{\mathfrak{S}^c} \rangle$, where $R_{\mathfrak{S}^c}(\alpha) = 1 - R_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha)$

Theorem 3.7.

Let $\mathfrak{S} = (P_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}}, R_{\mathfrak{S}})$ be a pythagorean neutrosophic set in a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$. Then $\mathfrak{S}$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic ideal of $\mathfrak{B}$ if and only if $\diamond \mathfrak{S} = \langle P_{\mathfrak{S}}, P_{\mathfrak{S}^c} \rangle$, $\square \mathfrak{S} = \langle Q_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}^c} \rangle$ and $\Delta \mathfrak{S} = \langle R_{\mathfrak{S}}, R_{\mathfrak{S}^c} \rangle$ are pythagorean neutrosophic ideals of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$.

Proof. Let $\mathfrak{S} = (P_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}}, R_{\mathfrak{S}})$ be a pythagorean neutrosophic ideal of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$, then $P_{\mathfrak{S}} = (P_{\mathfrak{S}^c})^c$, $Q_{\mathfrak{S}^c}$ and $R_{\mathfrak{S}^c}$ are neutrosophic ideal of $\mathfrak{B}$, hence $\diamond \mathfrak{S} = \langle P_{\mathfrak{S}}, P_{\mathfrak{S}^c} \rangle$, $\square \mathfrak{S} = \langle Q_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}^c} \rangle$ and $\Delta \mathfrak{S} = \langle R_{\mathfrak{S}}, R_{\mathfrak{S}^c} \rangle$ are pythagorean neutrosophic ideals of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$.

Conversely, if $\diamond \mathfrak{S} = \langle P_{\mathfrak{S}}, P_{\mathfrak{S}^c} \rangle$, $\square \mathfrak{S} = \langle Q_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}^c} \rangle$ and

$\Delta \mathfrak{S} = \langle R_{\mathfrak{S}}, R_{\mathfrak{S}^c} \rangle$ are pythagorean neutrosophic ideals of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$. Then the neutrosophic sets $P_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}^c}$ and $R_{\mathfrak{S}^c}$ is a neutrosophic ideal of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$.

Hence PNS $\mathfrak{S} = (P_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}}, R_{\mathfrak{S}})$ be a pythagorean neutrosophic ideals of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$.

□

Theorem 3.8.

A pythagorean neutrosophic set $\mathfrak{S} = (P_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}}, R_{\mathfrak{S}})$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic ideal of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$ if and only if for all $v, \zeta \in [0, 1]$ the non-empty set $U(\mathfrak{S}: v)$ and $L(\mathfrak{S}: \zeta)$ are ideals of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$.

Proof. Let pythagorean neutrosophic set $\mathfrak{S} = (P_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}}, R_{\mathfrak{S}})$ be a pythagorean neutrosophic ideal of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$.

$\Rightarrow$ For any $v, \zeta \in [0, 1]$, let $\alpha, \varphi \in U(\mathfrak{S}: v)$, then $P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha) \geq v$ and $P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi) \geq v$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned}
P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha - \varphi) &\geq \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\
&\geq v.
\end{aligned}$$

and so $\alpha - \varphi \in U(\mathfrak{S}: v)$.

$\Rightarrow$ For any $\alpha \in U(\mathfrak{S}: v)$ and $\varphi \in \mathfrak{B}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) &\geq \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \\
&\geq v.
\end{aligned}$$

and so $\alpha \varphi \in U(\mathfrak{S}: v)$.

$\Rightarrow$ For any $\alpha \in U(\mathfrak{S}:v)$ and $\varphi \in \mathfrak{B}$, we get

$$P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) \geq P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha) \geq v.$$

and so $\varphi + \alpha - \varphi \in U(\mathfrak{S}:v)$.

$\Rightarrow$ For any $\alpha \in \mathfrak{B}$ and $\varphi \in U(\mathfrak{S}:v)$, we get

$$P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \geq P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi) \geq v.$$

and so $\alpha \varphi \in U(\mathfrak{S}:v)$.

$\Rightarrow$ For any $\alpha, \varphi \in \mathfrak{B}$ and $\varepsilon \in U(\mathfrak{S}:v)$, we get

$$P_{\mathfrak{S}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) \geq P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varepsilon) \geq v.$$

and so $(\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi \in U(\mathfrak{S}:v)$.

Therefore, $U(\mathfrak{S}:v)$ is an ideal of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$. Again let $\alpha, \varphi \in L(\mathfrak{S}:\zeta)$, then $Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha) \leq \zeta$ and $Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi) \leq \zeta$. Hence

$$Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha - \varphi) \leq \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \leq \zeta.$$

and so $\alpha - \varphi \in L(\mathfrak{S}:\zeta)$.

$\Rightarrow$ For any $\alpha \in L(\mathfrak{S}:\zeta)$ and $\varphi \in \mathfrak{B}$, we get

$$Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \leq \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi)\} \leq \zeta.$$

and so $\alpha \varphi \in L(\mathfrak{S}:\zeta)$.

$\Rightarrow$ For any $\alpha \in L(\mathfrak{S}:\zeta)$ and $\varphi \in \mathfrak{B}$, we get

$$Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) \leq Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha) \leq \zeta.$$

and so $\varphi + \alpha - \varphi \in L(\mathfrak{S}:\zeta)$.

$\Rightarrow$ Moreover for any $\alpha \in \mathfrak{B}$ and $\varphi \in L(\mathfrak{S}:\zeta)$, we get

$$Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha \varphi) \leq Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varphi) \leq \zeta.$$

and so $\alpha \varphi \in L(\mathfrak{S}:\zeta)$.

$\Rightarrow$ Finally for any $\alpha, \varphi \in \mathfrak{B}$ and $\varepsilon \in L(\mathfrak{S}:\zeta)$, we get

$$Q_{\mathfrak{S}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) \leq Q_{\mathfrak{S}}(\varepsilon) \leq \zeta.$$

and so $(\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi \in L(\mathfrak{S}:\zeta)$.

Therefore, $L(\mathfrak{S}:\zeta)$ is an ideals of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$. Similarly we get $R_{\mathfrak{S}}$ is also $L(\mathfrak{S}:\zeta)$ is an ideals of a near-ring $\mathfrak{B}$. □

Theorem 3.9.

Let $\mathfrak{B}$ be a near-ring. Then the following are true.

- (1) The intersection of two pythagorean neutrosophic subnear-ring of $\mathfrak{B}$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic subnear-ring of $\mathfrak{B}$.
- (2) The intersection of two pythagorean neutrosophic left(resp. right) ideal of $\mathfrak{B}$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic left(resp. right) ideal of $\mathfrak{B}$.

Proof. Let $\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}$ and $\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}$ be two pythagorean neutrosophic subnear-ring of $\mathfrak{B}$. Let $\alpha, \varphi, n \in \mathfrak{B}$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha - \varphi) &= \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha - \varphi), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha - \varphi)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varphi)\}, \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varphi)\}, \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\}\} \\ &= \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha - \varphi) &= \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha - \varphi), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha - \varphi)\} \\ &\leq \max\{\max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varphi)\}, \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\}\} \\ &= \max\{\max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varphi)\}, \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\}\} \\ &= \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha - \varphi) &= \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha - \varphi), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha - \varphi)\} \\ &\leq \max\{\max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varphi)\}, \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\}\} \\ &= \max\{\max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varphi)\}, \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\}\} \\ &= \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha \varphi) &= \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha \varphi), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha \varphi)\} \\
&\geq \min\{\min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varphi)\}, \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\}\} \\
&= \min\{\min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varphi)\}, \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\}\} \\
&= \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\} \\
Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha \varphi) &= \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha \varphi), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha \varphi)\} \\
&\leq \max\{\max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varphi)\}, \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\}\} \\
&= \max\{\max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varphi)\}, \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\}\} \\
&= \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\} \\
R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha \varphi) &= \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha \varphi), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha \varphi)\} \\
&\leq \max\{\max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varphi)\}, \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\}\} \\
&= \max\{\max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varphi)\}, \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\}\} \\
&= \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi)\}
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic subnear-ring of $\mathfrak{B}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Consider, } P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) &= \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi)\} \\
&\geq \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha)\} \\
&= P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha) \\
Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) &= \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi)\} \\
&\leq \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha)\} \\
&= Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha) \\
R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) &= \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi)\} \\
&\leq \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha)\} \\
&= R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha) \\
P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha \varphi) &= \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha \varphi), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha \varphi)\} \\
&\geq \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha)\} \\
&= P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha) \\
Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha \varphi) &= \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha \varphi), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha \varphi)\} \\
&\leq \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha)\} \\
&= Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha) \\
R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha \varphi) &= \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha \varphi), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha \varphi)\} \\
&\leq \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\alpha), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha)\} \\
&= R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\alpha) \\
P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) &= \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi)\} \\
&\geq \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varepsilon), P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varepsilon)\} \\
&= P_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varepsilon) \\
Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) &= \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi)\} \\
&\leq \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varepsilon), Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varepsilon)\} \\
&= Q_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varepsilon) \\
R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) &= \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi)\} \\
&\leq \max\{R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1}}(\varepsilon), R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varepsilon)\} \\
&= R_{\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}}(\varepsilon)
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\mathfrak{S}_{N_1} \cap \mathfrak{S}_{N_2}$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic left(resp right) ideal of $\mathfrak{B}$. □

Theorem 3.10.

Let $Y: \mathfrak{U} \rightarrow \mathfrak{B}$ be a homomorphism of near-ring. If PNS $\mathfrak{S} = (P_{\mathfrak{S}}, Q_{\mathfrak{S}}, R_{\mathfrak{S}})$ in $\mathfrak{B}$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic ideal of $\mathfrak{B}$, then PNS $Y^{-1}(\mathfrak{S})$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic ideal of $\mathfrak{U}$.

Proof. Let $\mathfrak{S}$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic fuzzy ideal of $\mathfrak{U}$. Let $\alpha, \varphi, \varepsilon \in \mathfrak{U}$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
Y^{-1}(P_{\mathfrak{S}}(\alpha - \varphi)) &= P_{\mathfrak{S}}(Y(\alpha - \varphi)) = P_{\mathfrak{S}}(Y(\alpha) - Y(\varphi)) \\
&\geq \min\{P_{\mathfrak{S}}(Y(\alpha)), P_{\mathfrak{S}}(Y(\varphi))\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \min\{Y^{-1}(P_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha)), Y^{-1}(P_{\mathfrak{E}}(\varphi))\} \\
Y^{-1}(Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha - \varphi)) &= Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha - \varphi)) = Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha) - Y(\varphi)) \\
&\leq \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha)), Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\varphi))\} \\
&= \max\{Y^{-1}(Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha)), Y^{-1}(Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(\varphi))\} \\
Y^{-1}(R_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha - \varphi)) &= R_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha - \varphi)) = R_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha) - Y(\varphi)) \\
&\leq \max\{R_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha)), R_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\varphi))\} \\
&= \max\{Y^{-1}(R_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha)), Y^{-1}(R_{\mathfrak{E}}(\varphi))\} \\
Y^{-1}(P_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha \varphi)) &= P_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha \varphi)) = P_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha)Y(\varphi)) \\
&\geq \min\{P_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha)), P_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\varphi))\} \\
&= \min\{Y^{-1}(P_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha)), Y^{-1}(P_{\mathfrak{E}}(\varphi))\} \\
Y^{-1}(Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha \varphi)) &= Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha \varphi)) = Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(l)Y(\varphi)) \\
&\leq \max\{Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha)), Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\varphi))\} \\
&= \max\{Y^{-1}(Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha)), Y^{-1}(Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(\varphi))\} \\
Y^{-1}(R_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha \varphi)) &= R_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha \varphi)) = R_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(l)Y(\varphi)) \\
&\leq \max\{R_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha)), R_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\varphi))\} \\
&= \max\{Y^{-1}(R_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha)), Y^{-1}(R_{\mathfrak{E}}(\varphi))\} \\
Y^{-1}(P_{\mathfrak{E}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi)) &= P_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi)) = P_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\varphi) + Y(\alpha) - Y(\varphi)) \\
&\geq P_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha)) \\
&= Y^{-1}(P_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha)) \\
Y^{-1}(Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi)) &= Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi)) = Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\varphi) + Y(\alpha) - Y(\varphi)) \\
&\leq Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha)) \\
&= Y^{-1}(Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha)) \\
Y^{-1}(R_{\mathfrak{E}}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi)) &= R_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi)) = R_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\varphi) + Y(\alpha) - Y(\varphi)) \\
&\leq R_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha)) \\
&= Y^{-1}(R_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha)) \\
Y^{-1}(P_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha \varphi)) &= P_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha \varphi)) = P_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha)Y(\varphi)) \\
&\geq P_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\varphi)) \\
&= Y^{-1}(P_{\mathfrak{E}}(\varphi)) \\
Y^{-1}(Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha \varphi)) &= Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha \varphi)) = Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha)Y(\varphi)) \\
&\leq Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\varphi)) \\
&= Y^{-1}(Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(\varphi)) \\
Y^{-1}(R_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha \varphi)) &= R_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha \varphi)) = R_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\alpha)Y(\varphi)) \\
&\leq R_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\varphi)) \\
&= Y^{-1}(R_{\mathfrak{E}}(\varphi)) \\
Y^{-1}(P_{\mathfrak{E}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi)) &= P_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi)) \\
&= P_{\mathfrak{E}}((Y(\alpha) + Y(\varepsilon))Y(\varphi) - Y(\alpha)Y(\varphi)) \\
&\geq P_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\varepsilon)) \\
&= Y^{-1}(P_{\mathfrak{E}}(\varepsilon)) \\
Y^{-1}(Q_{\mathfrak{E}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi)) &= Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi)) \\
&= Q_{\mathfrak{E}}((Y(\alpha) + Y(\varepsilon))Y(\varphi) - Y(\alpha)Y(\varphi)) \\
&\leq Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\varepsilon)) \\
&= Y^{-1}(Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(\varepsilon)) \\
Y^{-1}(R_{\mathfrak{E}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi)) &= R_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi)) \\
&= R_{\mathfrak{E}}((Y(\alpha) + Y(\varepsilon))Y(\varphi) - Y(\alpha)Y(\varphi)) \\
&\leq R_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\varepsilon)) \\
&= Y^{-1}(R_{\mathfrak{E}}(\varepsilon))
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $Y^{-1}(\mathfrak{E})$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic ideal of $\mathfrak{B}$. □

The converse of the above theorem with stronger condition on Y can be stated as follows.

Theorem 3.11.

Let $Y: \mathfrak{U} \rightarrow \mathfrak{B}$ be an epimorphism of near-rings. Let PNS $\mathfrak{E} = (P_{\mathfrak{E}}, Q_{\mathfrak{E}}, R_{\mathfrak{E}})$ in $\mathfrak{B}$. Such that $Y^{-1}(\mathfrak{E})$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic ideal of $\mathfrak{U}$ then $\mathfrak{E}$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic ideal of $\mathfrak{B}$.

Proof. Let $\alpha, \varphi, \varepsilon \in \mathfrak{B}$. Then $Y(v) = \alpha, Y(\zeta) = \varphi$ and $Y(\tau) = \varepsilon$ for some $v, \zeta, \tau \in \mathfrak{U}$. It follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
P_{\mathfrak{E}}(\alpha - \varphi) &= P_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(v) - Y(\zeta)) = P_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(v - \zeta)) = Y^{-1}(P_{\mathfrak{E}}(v - \zeta)) \\
&\geq \min\{Y^{-1}(P_{\mathfrak{E}}(v)), Y^{-1}(P_{\mathfrak{E}}(\zeta))\} \\
&= \min\{P_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(v)), P_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\zeta))\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \min\{P_{\varepsilon}(\alpha), P_{\varepsilon}(\varphi)\} \\
Q_{\varepsilon}(\alpha - \varphi) &= Q_{\varepsilon}(Y(v) - Y(\zeta)) = Q_{\varepsilon}(Y(v - \zeta)) = Y^{-1}(Q_{\varepsilon}(v - \zeta)) \\
&\leq \max\{Y^{-1}(Q_{\varepsilon}(v)), Y^{-1}(Q_{\varepsilon}(\zeta))\} \\
&= \max\{Q_{\varepsilon}(Y(v)), Q_{\varepsilon}(Y(\zeta))\} \\
&= \max\{Q_{\varepsilon}(\alpha), Q_{\varepsilon}(\varphi)\} \\
R_{\varepsilon}(\alpha - \varphi) &= R_{\varepsilon}(Y(v) - Y(\zeta)) = R_{\varepsilon}(Y(v - \zeta)) = Y^{-1}(R_{\varepsilon}(v - \zeta)) \\
&\leq \max\{Y^{-1}(R_{\varepsilon}(v)), Y^{-1}(R_{\varepsilon}(\zeta))\} \\
&= \max\{R_{\varepsilon}(Y(v)), R_{\varepsilon}(Y(\zeta))\} \\
&= \max\{R_{\varepsilon}(\alpha), R_{\varepsilon}(\varphi)\} \\
P_{\varepsilon}(\alpha \varphi) &= P_{\varepsilon}(Y(v)Y(\zeta)) = P_{\varepsilon}(Y(v\zeta)) = Y^{-1}(P_{\varepsilon}(v\zeta)) \\
&\geq \min\{Y^{-1}(P_{\varepsilon}(v)), Y^{-1}(P_{\varepsilon}(\zeta))\} \\
&= \min\{P_{\varepsilon}(Y(v)), P_{\varepsilon}(Y(\zeta))\} \\
&= \min\{P_{\varepsilon}(\alpha), P_{\varepsilon}(\varphi)\} \\
Q_{\varepsilon}(\alpha \varphi) &= Q_{\varepsilon}(Y(v)Y(\zeta)) = Q_{\varepsilon}(Y(v\zeta)) = Y^{-1}(Q_{\varepsilon}(v\zeta)) \\
&\leq \max\{Y^{-1}(Q_{\varepsilon}(v)), Y^{-1}(Q_{\varepsilon}(\zeta))\} \\
&= \max\{Q_{\varepsilon}(Y(v)), Q_{\varepsilon}(Y(\zeta))\} \\
&= \max\{Q_{\varepsilon}(\alpha), Q_{\varepsilon}(\varphi)\} \\
R_{\varepsilon}(\alpha \varphi) &= R_{\varepsilon}(Y(v)Y(\zeta)) = R_{\varepsilon}(Y(v\zeta)) = Y^{-1}(R_{\varepsilon}(v\zeta)) \\
&\leq \max\{Y^{-1}(R_{\varepsilon}(v)), Y^{-1}(R_{\varepsilon}(\zeta))\} \\
&= \max\{R_{\varepsilon}(Y(v)), R_{\varepsilon}(Y(\zeta))\} \\
&= \max\{R_{\varepsilon}(\alpha), R_{\varepsilon}(\zeta)\} \\
P_{\varepsilon}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) &= P_{\varepsilon}(Y(\zeta) + Y(v) - Y(\zeta)) = P_{\varepsilon}(Y(\zeta + v - \zeta)) \\
&= Y^{-1}(P_{\varepsilon}(\zeta + v - \zeta)) \\
&\geq Y^{-1}(P_{\varepsilon}(v)) \\
&= P_{\varepsilon}(Y(v)) \\
&= P_{\varepsilon}(\alpha) \\
Q_{\varepsilon}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) &= Q_{\varepsilon}(Y(\zeta) + Y(v) - Y(\zeta)) = Q_{\varepsilon}(Y(\zeta + v - \zeta)) \\
&= Y^{-1}(Q_{\varepsilon}(\zeta + v - \zeta)) \\
&\leq Y^{-1}(Q_{\varepsilon}(v)) \\
&= Q_{\varepsilon}(Y(v)) \\
&= Q_{\varepsilon}(\alpha) \\
R_{\varepsilon}(\varphi + \alpha - \varphi) &= R_{\varepsilon}(Y(\zeta) + Y(v) - Y(\zeta)) = R_{\varepsilon}(Y(\zeta + v - \zeta)) \\
&= Y^{-1}(R_{\varepsilon}(\zeta + v - \zeta)) \\
&\leq Y^{-1}(R_{\varepsilon}(v)) \\
&= R_{\varepsilon}(Y(v)) \\
&= R_{\varepsilon}(\alpha) \\
P_{\varepsilon}(\alpha \varphi) &= P_{\varepsilon}(Y(v)Y(\zeta)) = P_{\varepsilon}(Y(v\zeta)) = Y^{-1}(P_{\varepsilon}(v\zeta)) \\
&\geq Y^{-1}(P_{\varepsilon}(\zeta)) \\
&= P_{\varepsilon}(Y(\zeta)) \\
&= P_{\varepsilon}(\varphi) \\
Q_{\varepsilon}(\alpha \varphi) &= Q_{\varepsilon}(Y(v)Y(\zeta)) = Q_{\varepsilon}(Y(v\zeta)) = Y^{-1}(Q_{\varepsilon}(v\zeta)) \\
&\leq Y^{-1}(Q_{\varepsilon}(\zeta)) \\
&= Q_{\varepsilon}(Y(\zeta)) \\
&= Q_{\varepsilon}(\varphi) \\
R_{\varepsilon}(\alpha \varphi) &= R_{\varepsilon}(Y(v)Y(\zeta)) = R_{\varepsilon}(Y(v\zeta)) = Y^{-1}(R_{\varepsilon}(v\zeta)) \\
&\leq Y^{-1}(R_{\varepsilon}(\zeta)) \\
&= R_{\varepsilon}(Y(\zeta)) \\
&= R_{\varepsilon}(\varphi) \\
P_{\varepsilon}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) &= P_{\varepsilon}((Y(v) + Y(\tau))Y(\zeta) - Y(v)Y(\zeta)) = P_{\varepsilon}(Y((v + \tau)\zeta - v\zeta)) \\
&= Y^{-1}(P_{\varepsilon}((v + \tau)\zeta - v\zeta)) \\
&\geq Y^{-1}(P_{\varepsilon}(\tau)) \\
&= P_{\varepsilon}(Y(\tau)) \\
&= P_{\varepsilon}(\varepsilon) \\
Q_{\varepsilon}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) &= Q_{\varepsilon}((Y(v) + Y(\tau))Y(\zeta) - Y(v)Y(\zeta)) = Q_{\varepsilon}(Y((v + \tau)\zeta - v\zeta)) \\
&= Y^{-1}(Q_{\varepsilon}((v + \tau)\zeta - v\zeta)) \\
&\leq Y^{-1}(Q_{\varepsilon}(\tau))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\tau)) \\
&= Q_{\mathfrak{E}}(\varepsilon) \\
R_{\mathfrak{E}}((\alpha + \varepsilon)\varphi - \alpha \varphi) &= R_{\mathfrak{E}}\left(\left(Y(v) + Y(\tau)\right)Y(\zeta) - Y(v)Y(\zeta)\right) = R_{\mathfrak{E}}\left(Y\left((v + \tau)\zeta - v\zeta\right)\right) \\
&= Y^{-1}\left(R_{\mathfrak{E}}\left((v + \tau)\zeta - v\zeta\right)\right) \\
&\leq Y^{-1}\left(R_{\mathfrak{E}}(\tau)\right) \\
&= R_{\mathfrak{E}}(Y(\tau)) \\
&= R_{\mathfrak{E}}(\varepsilon)
\end{aligned}$$

Hence $\text{PNS } \mathfrak{E} = (P_{\mathfrak{E}}, Q_{\mathfrak{E}}, R_{\mathfrak{E}})$ is a pythagorean neutrosophic ideal of $\mathfrak{u}$.

□

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have defined pythagorean neutrosophic ideals and intersection of two pythagorean neutrosophic ideals. Also discussed some important properties of pythagorean neutrosophic ideals in near-ring with examples. In our future study of this article describe pythagorean neutrosophic bi-ideals of near ring.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to thank Dr.K.Lenin Muthu Kumaran and also very much grateful to the referee for their valuable comments and suggestions for improving this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1]. M. Abdel-Basset , M. Manogaran , M. Mohamed, M.A. Rayan . A neutrosophic theory based security approach for $f \circ g$ and mobile-edge computing. *Computer Networks* . 157, pp. 122-132.
- [2]. A. Abou-zaid . On fuzzy subnear-rings. *Fuzzy sets and systems*.1989. vol. 81, pp.383-393.
- [3]. A.K. Adak, D. Darvishi Salokolaci. Some properties of pythagorean fuzzy ideals of near-rings. *International journal of applied operational research*. 2019. vol.9(3), pp. 1-9.
- [4]. V. Chinnadurai, A. Arul selvam. Interval valued pythagorean fuzzy ideals in semigroup. *Journal of fuzzy extension and application*. 2020. vol.1(4), pp. 293-303.
- [5]. B.C. Cuong . Picture fuzzy sets . *J Comput Sci cuberneIcs*.2014. vol.30(4), pp. 409-420.
- [6]. B. Davvaz. Fuzzy ideals of near-rings with interval valued membership functions. *Journal of sciences Islamic republic of Iran*. 2001. vol.12(2), pp. 171-175.
- [7]. H. Garg. A new generalized pythagorean fuzzy information aggregation using einstein operations and its application to decision making. *International Journal of intel systems*. 2017. vol.31(9), pp.886-920.
- [8]. F.K. Gundogdu, C. Kahraman. Properties and arithmetic operations of spherical fuzzy subsets. *Studies in fuzziness and soft computing*. 2018. pp.3-25.
- [9]. A. Hussain, T. Mahmood and M.I. Ali. Rough pythagorean fuzzy ideals in semigroups. *Computational and applied mathematics*. 2019. vol. 38(2), pp .67.
- [10]. Y.B. Jun , K.H. Kim. Intuitionistic fuzzy interior ideals of semigroups. *Int. J. Math. Sci*. 2001. vol. 27, pp.261-267.
- [11]. Y.B. Jun,K.H. Kim . Intuitionistic fuzzy ideals of semigroups. *Int. J. Pure appl. Math*. 2002. vol.33, pp. 443-449.
- [12]. Y.B. Jun , S. Lajos. On fuzzy (1,2)- ideals of semigroups. *PU. M, A*. 1997. vol.8, pp.335-338.
- [13]. M.S. Khan, Anis , F. Smarandache, Y.B. Jun. Neutrosophic N- structures and their applications in semigroups. *Annals of fuzzy mathematics and informatics*, reprint.
- [14]. K. Lenin Muthu Kumaran and A. Rajalakshmi . A note on anti neutrosophic fuzzy ideals of near-ring. *National conference on recent trends in physical science research with a mathematical approach*. 2023.
- [15]. M. Ramachandran and K. Dhilipkumar . Interval valued anti fuzzy weak bi-ideals of near-rings. *International journal of applied engineering research* , ISSN 0973-4562. 2018. vol.13(13), pp. 11336-11339.
- [16]. K.E. Sathappan and R. Sumathi. Regularity concept of L-fuzzy bi-ideals in near-rings. *Pramana research journal* ISSN 2249-2976.
- [17]. F. Samarandache. A unifying field in logics. Neutrosophic: Neutrosophic probability set and logic. *American research press*, rehoboth, mass, USA 1999.
- [18]. F. Samarandache . Neutrosophic set, a generalisation of the intuitionistic fuzzy sets. *Inter. J. Pure Appl. Math*. 2005. vol.24, pp. 287-297.
- [19]. A. Solairaju, S. Thiruvani. Neutrosophic fuzzy ideals of Near-rings. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*. 2018. vol.118(6), pp.527-539.

- [20]. R.R. Yager. Pythagorean fuzzy subsets. *In: Proc joint IFSA world congress and NAFIPS annual meeting, Edmonton, Canada.* 2013. pp. 57-61.
- [21]. L.A. Zadeh . Fuzzy Sets. *Inform and Control.* 1965. 8: 338-353.
- [22]. L.A. Zadeh. The concept of a linguistic variable and its application to approximate reasoning. *Inform. Sci.* 1975. vol.8, pp.199-249.